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E-mail: rasti@cc.iut.ac.ir

Mr. Mohsen FathollahBayati
Department of Industrial Engineering
Iran University of Science and Technology, Iran
E-mail: mfbayati@ind.iut.ac.ir

Dr. Edgardo Palza Vargas
Telfer School of Management
University of Ottawa, Canada
Email: edgardo.palza-vargas.1@ens.etsmtl.ca

Dr. Solomon Markos
Assistant Professor, School of Commerce
Addis Ababa University, Ethiopia
Email: solomonmarkos5@yahoo.com

Dr. OluOjo
Lecturer, Department of Business Administration
Osun State University, Nigeria
Email: oluojo@yahoo.com

Dr. Mohammed-AminuSanda
Visiting Research Fellow, Lulea University of Technology,
Sweden
Senior Lecturer, Department of Organization and Human
Resource Management, University of Ghana, Ghana
Email: masanda@ug.edu.gh

Dr. Khalid Zaman
Assistant Professor, Department of Economics,
University of Wah, Pakistan
Email: dr.khalidzaman@uow.edu.pk

Dr. KartinahAyupp
Deputy Dean, Economics and Business
Universiti Malaysia Sarawak, Malaysia
Email: akartinah@feb.unimas.my

Dr. Malyadri. Pacha
Principal, Government Degree College
Affiliated to Osmania University, India
Email: drpm16@yahoo.co.in

Dr. ArifAnjum
Assistant Professor, M.S.G. Arts, Science & Commerce
College, Malegaon, India
Managing Editor, International Journal of Management
Studies
Email: infoijcms@gmail.com

Mr. Andrew McCalister
Global Research Awardee, Royal Academy of Engineering,
University of Cambridge, UK
Email: andrewmccalister@gmail.com

Dr. MohsinShaikh
Professor & Head, Department of Management Studies
SKN College of Engineering, Pune, India
Email: skmohs@yahoo.co.in

Prof Dr. M Razaullah Khan
Professor and Head at Dept of Management and Commerce
Maulana Azad National Urdu University Hyderabad, India
Email: razakhan@manuu.edu.in

Mr. Kai Pan
Research Assistant & Ph.D. Candidate, Department of
Software and Information Systems
University of North Carolina (UNC Charlotte), USA
Email: kpan@unc.edu

Dr. SundarKumararaj
Associate Professor, Commerce Wing, Directorate of
Distance Education,
Annammalai University, Annammalai Nagar, Tamil Nadu, India
E-Mail: commercesundar@gmail.com

Dr. Mohammad Alawin
Associate Professor, Business Economics Department
The University of Jordan, Amman, Jordan
E-mail: m.alawin@ju.edu.jo

Mr. Dinh Tran Ngoc Huy
Visiting lecturer, PhD candidate, Banking University HCMC,
Vietnam
Email: dtnhuy2010@gmail.com

Dr. Cüneyt AKAR
Associate Professor, Department of Business Administration
BandirmaOnyediyülyul University, Turkey
Email: cakar@bandirma.edu.tr

Dr. Abdul HafazNghah
Senior Lecturer, School of Maritime Business and
Management,
Universiti Malaysia Terengganu, Malaysia
Email: hafaz.ngah@umt.edu.my

Mr. MostafaTorabi
Assistant Professor, Department of Business Administration
Brandon University, Canada
E-mail: torabim@brandonu.ca

Dr. Jia Chi Tsou
Associate Professor, Department of Business Administration
China University of Technology, Taiwan
E-mail: tsou.tw@yahoo.com.tw

Dr. JaynyaDuttaNayak
Assistant Professor, P.G. Department of Commerce
Khallokote Auto. College, Berhampur (Govt. College of
Odisha), India
E-mail: jaynya.dutta@gmail.com

Dr. Ionel BOSTAN
Professor DHC, Doctoral School of Economics,
Stefan cel Mare University of Suceava (Romania)
E-mail: ionel.bostan@fdsa.usv.ro

Web: <http://ijibm.elitehall.com>

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